

AI-Generated Text Detection in the Context of Domain- and Prompt-Specific Essays: a case study on self-assessment essays

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Abstract

The widespread use of large language models (LLMs) has made AI-generated writing nearly indistinguishable from human text, posing new challenges for educational, professional, and research domains. We propose a scalable and cost-effective AI detection framework tailored for domain-specific essays, combining traditional machine learning and fine-tuned deep learning models. Using self-regulated learning (SRL) essays from the Diagnostic Assessment and Achievement of College Skills (DAACS) as a case study, we created a synthetic dataset that simulates realistic hybrid human-AI writing. recall-tuned Random Forest (RF) baseline over MiniLM, DistilRoBERTa, and OpenAI embeddings with four ModernBERT heads that capture complementary signals: an essay-level classifier, a sentence-pair classifier, and two scalar scorers for coherence and style consistency. At inference time—without additional training—we aggregate these heads using three simple fusion strategies (Equal, Dynamic, Hierarchical) and report all three side-by-side. Results on held-out data show that essay-level and sentence-pair classifiers achieve weighted F1 scores above 0.97 and 0.92 respectively, while coherence and style regression models achieve R^2 scores of 0.93 and 0.78. The RF OvO baseline provides strong pairwise separability and controllable recall via threshold selection, while the ModernBERT heads add robustness on hybrid human–AI texts. The entire system is practical to deploy: deep models run on consumer-grade GPUs, and the RF baseline affords a CPU-only fallback. Overall, multi-view signals plus inference-time fusion yield a high-recall, interpretable, and hardware-friendly approach to domain-specific AI detection.

Key Words: AI Detection, DAACS, Domain-Specific Texts, ModernBERT, Embeddings, Random Forest, Educational Assessment

1. Introduction

The growing availability of large language models (LLMs) such as chatGPT has profoundly changed how written content is produced across education, business, and research. These systems can generate fluent, coherent, and contextually relevant prose on demand, making it increasingly difficult to determine whether a text was written by a human or an artificial intelligence. This technological progress has created both opportunities for creativity and serious challenges for authenticity, assessment, and trust.

In educational settings, for example, essays are often used as diagnostic or formative tools to evaluate self-reflection, comprehension, and writing ability. When students or professionals rely on generative AI systems to produce or edit their work, evaluators risk misinterpreting the results. Conventional AI detectors that focus on general linguistic cues or probability distributions perform poorly when applied to domain-specific or prompt-constrained writing, where style, tone, and vocabulary are generally uniform. This study was conducted in the context of an online diagnostic assessment system, DAACS, that is designed as a tool to support students' academic success from

the very beginning of their college career. This highlights the need for robust detection approaches designed specifically for narrow contexts and specialized writing tasks.

This study introduces a novel framework for detecting AI-generated and hybrid (human-AI) texts within domain-specific essays. The objective is to develop models that are easy to implement, computationally efficient, and capable of maintaining high recall without excessive false positives. The framework combines traditional machine-learning and transformer-based deep-learning approaches to capture complementary global and local features of writing. It further introduces synthetic data generation methods that reproduce realistic patterns of AI use, including human-authored essays modified or polished by AI systems.

The contributions of this research are fourfold:

1. Construction of a heterogeneous dataset of human, AI, and hybrid essays that reflect real-world authorship practices within a structured writing prompt.
2. Development of a multi-level detection pipeline that integrates traditional Random Forest models with fine-tuned ModernBERT architectures for essay-level, sentence-pair, coherence, and style-consistency analysis.
3. Proposal of inference focused ensemble fusion strategies that combines training results of all models into a comprehensible and transparent output.
4. Comprehensive evaluation demonstrating that the combined approach achieves high recall (≥ 0.9) and strong generalization, even when tested on subtle hybrid cases.

This work demonstrates that effective and affordable AI-generated text detection is possible in specialized domains. The approach not only enhances reliability for educational and professional assessments but also establishes a scalable blueprint for trustworthy authorship verification in other high-stakes or regulated writing environments.

2. Background and Related Work

Efforts to detect AI-generated text have evolved rapidly since the public release of chat-based LLMs in late 2022. Early detectors relied on linguistic irregularities, token probabilities, or perplexity scores, but these approaches can falter when domain context and prompt constraints narrow stylistic variability (Tang et al., 2023). Generic tools struggle to generalize across domains like reflective essays, where stylistic overlap between human and AI writing is high.

Recent studies demonstrate that embedding-based and transformer-based classifiers can achieve higher precision when fine-tuned on domain-specific corpora. However, production systems also need high recall, low computational overhead, and transparent failure modes, requirements that are underrepresented in prior literature.

Several recent works have incorporated textual coherence and style-consistency measures into AI-generated text detection pipelines. Liu et al. (2023) introduces a detector that explicitly models discourse coherence to improve AI text detection. They construct an *entity coherence graph* based on Centering Theory, treating entities as nodes and linking sentences via shared entities to capture sentence-to-sentence interactions. Zeng et al. (2024) study specifically tackles hybrid texts (e.g. student essays with mixed human and ChatGPT content) in an educational context. The authors propose a two-step pipeline: (1) segment the document to find boundaries where authorship

changes (each segment should have consistent style/author), and (2) classify each segment as human-written or AI-generated.

In this paper, we take a domain-first perspective: we design models and evaluation around a single, well-defined prompt family so that results reflect realistic operating conditions. Our pipeline combines: (i) lightweight traditional ML baselines (Random Forest over multiple embedding families) optimized for recall via multi-threshold selection and weighted voting; and (ii) a multi-level deep-learning stack based on ModernBERT that captures global document signals, local sentence transitions, and discourse/style regularities.

2.1 DAACS Writing Assessment Context

This study was conducted in the context of an online diagnostic assessment system, **DAACS**, designed to support students' academic success from the very beginning of their college careers. DAACS, short for Diagnostic Assessment and Achievement of College Skills, is a free, open source online assessment platform that offers students targeted feedback and resources to use (<https://daacs.net>). DAACS addresses four areas that have been shown to be important to the success in college: self-regulated learning (SRL), Writing, Reading, and Math. For this study, we focus on the Writing and SRL assessments (Akhmedjanova et al., 2019; Lui et al., 2018).

For the writing assessment, students are tasked with reflecting on and writing about their SRL strengths and weaknesses based on their results and feedback. As a part of the prompt, they are also asked to identify and commit to strategies to try. Figure 1 shows the writing assessment prompt. DAACS was first implemented in 2016-2017, when AI platforms were not yet freely and easily accessible. Thus, the chances of the essays submitted by students then are unlikely to be AI-generated essays. This is the dataset we used for this project.

You received information about your learning skills after you took the self-regulated learning (SRL) survey, as well as suggestions for becoming a more effective and efficient learner. Now, in order to reflect on your learning skills and receive feedback on your writing, please use the results from your SRL survey to do your best writing in a brief essay that answers the questions below.

You will need to refer to your SRL survey results and feedback in your essay. We recommend reviewing them, taking notes, and then returning here to write.

Essays must be at least 350 words in order to be meaningfully scored. Please aim to write a complete, well-developed essay in order to get accurate feedback about how ready you are for academic writing, and what you can do to strengthen your writing skills.

- What do your self-regulated learning survey results and the feedback tell you about your learning skills? Use results from the survey and the feedback to support your analysis.
- Which suggested strategies from the feedback are you committed to using this term? Explain why you are committed to using those strategies.

Figure 1. DAACS Writing Assessment Prompt (verbatim)

3. Methods

3.1 Dataset Construction and Prompt Engineering

This study uses a four-way labeling scheme designed to reflect realistic authorship patterns in domain-specific writing tasks. We combine the human-authored corpus with synthetic corpora that simulate common ways students may use AI—either to generate an essay outright or to edit/rehabilitate an existing text.

3.1.1 Corpus and Labels

We curate a four-class corpus aligned to realistic authorship modes within the DAACS SRL writing task. The taxonomy distinguishes **pure sources** (human-only, machine-only) from **hybrid pathways** in which AI tools revise an existing text. This design mirrors how writing assistance might be used in practice and allows models to learn signals that differ between *generation* and *editing* workflows. The labels and corpus description is provided below:

- **HUMAN (non-synthetic)** — *1,574 essays*. Historical DAACS essays authored in 2016–2017, before generative AI was widely accessible in education. These texts satisfy the DAACS minimum length requirement (≥ 350 words) and directly address the SRL reflection prompt (Figure 1). All essays are de-identified prior to use.
- **MG (Machine-Generated)** — *1,275 essays*. Essays produced directly by LLMs from the DAACS prompt using Prompt 1 (Sec. 3.1.2).
- **HG_MOD (Human → AI-Modified)** — *2,160 essays*. Human essays transformed by controlled AI rewriting operations (Prompt 2; Sec. 3.1.3) to simulate polishing/editing workflows.
- **MG_MOD (Machine → AI-Modified)** — *3,010 essays*. Machine-generated essays regenerated or revised by a *different* LLM (Prompt 2), increasing heterogeneity and reducing model-specific artifacts.

Human texts were written within DAACS, a *diagnostic* (not for course credit) assessment used to provide formative feedback. Students complete the SRL reflection as part of onboarding and receive guidance based on their responses; essays are not graded for transcript purposes. This low-stakes, feedback-oriented setting reduces strategic writing aimed at maximizing grades and provides a naturalistic baseline of human-written responses. The human essays then predate modern LLMs, minimizing AI-contamination risk. We normalize Unicode, strip markup, and remove duplicates (exact and trivial near-duplicates). For synthetic classes, we retain metadata for each sample—LLM family/version, prompt-variant ID, rewriting technique, and a hashed source essay ID. These metadata enable **grouped, stratified splitting** (70/15/15) so that all variants derived from a given base essay (e.g., a HUMAN essay and its HG_MOD children) remain within the *same* split, preventing leakage of near-identical texts across train/validation/test. We also track token counts to monitor length distributions and filter pathological outputs (e.g., bullet lists, meta-comments, or responses that do not meet prompt constraints).

In high-conformity domains, detecting “AI vs. human” alone is insufficient; the hybrid categories HG_MOD and MG_MOD often exhibit subtle coherence/style disruptions that differ from purely generated essays. Explicit labels for these pathways make the downstream models more diagnostic and useful for formative settings.

3.1.2 Prompt 1: Direct Machine Generation (MG)

The goal was to produce complete essays that plausibly satisfy the DAACS writing task while introducing controlled variability in tone, perspective, and structure.

We designed a two-part prompt, user and system for direct essay generation. We pair the **user prompt** (the DAACS SRL reflection task; Figure 1) presented verbatim with a **system prompt** comprising three components, to structure content and diversify outputs:

1. **SRL knowledge framework.** Formal definitions of SRL domains/subdomains (e.g., goal-setting, time management, metacognition) to anchor content and encourage topical coverage.
2. **Writing instructions.** A pool of nine guidance statements that shape rhetorical choices (e.g., “*Mention realistic constraints or self-doubt that adds authenticity to your reflection;*” “*Use a varied vocabulary, but avoid over-polished language.*”). At generation time we sample 3 of 9 instructions to avoid stylistic fixation.
3. **Style controls.** A catalog of tones and perspectives/identities (Figure 2). For each request we sample three tones and one perspective (e.g., *optimistic, reflective; freshman in college; working student*) to diversify voice.

Figure 2. Writing tones and perspectives

To further increase heterogeneity, we instructed the LLM to generate original and unique content by alternating the system prompt composition by (a) randomly include or omit the SRL definition block; (b) randomly selecting three out of the nine writing instruction statements and 3) randomly selecting three tones and one perspective per request; and (d) request three distinct essays per API call.

We generate MG texts with multiple LLM families (e.g., Claude 3.5 Sonnet, GPT-4o, Llama 3.1-405B). Mixing vendors/models reduces overfitting to a single model’s stylistic fingerprint and better reflects a realistic ecosystem in which students may use different tools.

3.1.3 Prompt 2: AI Modifications (HG_MOD and MG_MOD)

We designed a second two-part prompt to simulate realistic “AI editing” behaviors: The system prompt, distinctly from the previous prompt, consists of one simple instruction and the system prompt consists of different rewriting techniques and instructions, following a similar concept as in (Abassy et al., 2024).

- **System prompt:** “You are simulating an AI tool that students might use to enhance, modify, or adjust their essay. The essay must always be written in the first person, as if the student is reflecting on their learning process.”
- **User prompt:** one of six **rewriting techniques** applied to the *original* essay (human or machine), with technique-specific instructions, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Operationally, for each source essay we issue **six API calls**—one per technique—yielding six distinct variants. In this prompt, there is **no explicit DAACS/SRL definition text** provided to the model beyond what appears in the original essay, ensuring edits draw primarily from the essay’s own content.

Method	Instruction
Paraphrase	Please rewrite the following essay using paraphrasing techniques while preserving the meaning. Ensure the essay is still of same size or around 350 words. The output is just the essay, nothing else: {essay}
Summarize	Please summarize the following essay, but then expand it back to around 350 words based on the summarized content. The output is just the essay, nothing else: {essay}
Machine-Humanized	Please subtly modify the following essay to make it more human-like, enhance its relatability, and increase its overall human quality. Ensure the essay is still of same size or around 350 words. The output is just the essay, nothing else: {essay}
Machine-Polished	Please refine the following essay to correct grammar, improve style, enhance flow, and optimize readability while preserving its original meaning. Ensure the essay is still of same size or around 350 words. The output is just the essay, nothing else: {essay}
Tone-Adjustment	Please adjust the tone of the following essay to make it more formal or more casual, depending on the original tone. Ensure the essay is still of same size or around 350 words. The output is just the essay, nothing else: {essay}
Rewriting	Please rewrite the following essay using advanced rewriting techniques while keeping the core message intact. Ensure the essay is still of same size or around 350 words. The output is just the essay, nothing else: {essay}

Figure 3. Rewriting techniques

3.1.4 Data Splits and Preprocessing

We tokenize and store texts after light normalization (whitespace and encoding), preserving reflective first-person voice signals. For all supervised training, we use a **70/15/15** split (train/validation/test) applied **stratified by class** to maintain label balance across splits.

3.2 Traditional Machine Learning Baseline

As a lightweight, transparent baseline, we train Random Forest (RF) classifiers over fixed sentence-embedding vectors (Frohling and Zubiaga, 2021). This choice emphasizes operational simplicity (no fine-tuning), low cost (CPU-friendly inference), and *robustness* (insensitivity to feature scaling), while still allowing rigorous evaluation via ROC/AUC and recall-oriented thresholding.

3.2.1 Featurization and Pairwise Formulation

Each essay is embedded once using three families that span efficiency–capacity trade-offs. Embeddings are used as-is (no additional normalization) to preserve the geometry imposed by each model:

- **MiniLM** (384-dim) — compact, fast, free; suitable for local/edge inference.
- **DistilRoBERTa** (768-dim) — higher capacity while remaining free/open.
- **OpenAI** (1,536-dim) — highest-capacity vectors in our stack; paid but inexpensive per call.

Rather than training a single 4-way classifier, we decompose the task into **six One-vs-One (OvO)** binaries:

HUMAN↔MG, HUMAN↔HG_MOD, HUMAN↔MG_MOD, MG↔HG_MOD,
MG↔MG_MOD, HG_MOD↔MG_MOD.

For each pair and each embedding family we train a separate RF. This yields a grid of candidate models whose decision functions are specialized to the idiosyncrasies of that pair (e.g., *HUMAN* vs *MG* is much easier than *HG_MOD* vs *MG_MOD*).

We decided to use OvO and not a single multiclass RF for the following reasons (results to be discussed in section 4):

1. **Pair-specific separability.** Some boundaries (e.g., HUMAN vs MG) should be linearly separable in embedding space ($AUC \approx 1.0$), while hybrid-vs-hybrid is not. OvO lets each pair’s decision surface adapt to its own geometry instead of compromising on a single multiclass plane.
2. **Recall control per pair.** False-negative cost is asymmetrical across pairs. By calibrating thresholds per binary task we can enforce stricter recall where needed (e.g., MG or MG_MOD detection) without inflating false positives across the board.
3. **Interpretability and diagnostics.** OvO exposes ROC curves and AUC *per pair*; this is valuable for deployment discussions and for guiding fusion weights.
4. **Robustness to label frequency and overlap.** Hybrids (HG_MOD, MG_MOD) partially overlap in style/coherence; a single multiclass model tends to blur such boundaries. OvO avoids “winner-takes-all” competition among four logits and lets hard pairs receive dedicated capacity.

3.2.2 Training, Validation, and Recall-Threshold Selection

We split the corpus **70/15/15** (train/validation/test) using grouped, stratified sampling (Sec. 3.1.1) so that *all variants derived from a given base essay* stay in the same split—preventing leakage from near-duplicates. Class imbalance in pairwise tasks is minor because each pair is sampled in a balanced fashion.

For each pair/embedding we:

1. Fit an RF on the training set (using a small hyperparameter search around number of trees and depth; details in Appendix A).
2. Score the validation set to obtain probability outputs and the **ROC** curve.
3. **Evaluate three operating points** that target **minimum recall** levels:

$$T = \{0.50, 0.65, 0.80\}.$$

Concretely, for each $\tau \in \mathcal{T}$ we choose the probability cutoff that **achieves at least τ recall** on the positive class in validation.

4. Select the variant that **meets the recall target** while maximizing validation **F1** (or, when ties occur, maximizing **AUC**).
5. **Persist** the model’s validation statistics, the chosen cutoff, and its **ROC arrays (FPR/TPR) and AUC** in a per-model metadata file.

Our analysis script then ingests these metadata to create **ROC by embedding**, **ROC by threshold**, and **ROC by pairplots**, as well as **AUC distributions** and “best ROC” summaries. This is how we quantify which embedding works best per pair and how recall targets affect trade-offs. Across 3 embeddings \times 6 pairs \times 3 thresholds, this yields 54 trained models.

We prioritize recall with the use of recall thresholds, because in our application, missing AI-generated content (false negatives) is costlier than flagging an occasional human essay (false positives). The $\{0.50, 0.65, 0.80\}$ grid provides graduated safety levels. Lower τ gives broader coverage with fewer false alarms; higher τ tightens the net against AI content. We found that many pairs concentrate recall between 0.90 and 0.97 after selection (results discussed in section 4), indicating that the recall-targeting procedure successfully identifies high-recall operating points without collapsing precision.

3.2.3 Multi-Class Inference via Weighted Voting

At test time, a new essay is routed through all six OvO classifiers. Each classifier casts a vote for one of its two labels; we aggregate votes in two weighting modes:

- **F1-Weighted:** weight for classifier c equals its validation F1 $_c$.
- **Balanced-Weighted:** weight equals a recall-centric score that rewards high recall while penalizing large precision–recall gaps:

$$w_c = \text{Recall}_c - \lambda \cdot \left| \text{Recall}_c - \text{Precision}_c \right| \quad (\lambda \in [0, 1]), \text{ where } \lambda \text{ fixed in validation; see Appendix for exact value}$$

The class with the largest **total weighted vote** is returned. Switching between the two modes lets practitioners trade false-negative risk (recall) against precision, without retraining.

3.3 Deep Learning Pipeline

We fine-tuned four ModernBERT-based models (Warner et al. 2024), each capturing complementary textual dimensions such as global document signals, local sentence-to-sentence dynamics, and continuous discourse/style regularities. The stack comprises four models:

1. **Essay-Level Classifier** (4-way): an essay-level classifier that performs global classification of entire essays, it predicts labels {HUMAN, MG, HG_MOD, MG_MOD}
2. **Sentence-Pair Classifier** (4-way): a sentence-pair classifier trained on approximately 130k adjacent sentence pairs to detect local, short-range transitions characteristic of human vs. AI edits.
3. **Coherence Scorer** (regression): a coherence scorer implemented as a regression model that estimates discourse coherence/flow on a continuous scale (target range ≈ 0.3 – 1.0).
4. **Style-Consistency Scorer** (regression): a style consistency scorer implemented as a regression model detecting stylistic uniformity between adjacent sentences (target range ≈ 0 – 1.0).

Together, these models offer complementary views of the same text: the first two produce categorical evidence at different granularities, while the latter two provide continuous, interpretable signals that are useful at inference time for stabilizing borderline cases. These models provide robust, partially independent evidence streams that we later combine for inference tasks via the fusion strategies in §3.3.10.

3.3.1 Backbone, Tokenization, and Inputs

All models share a ModernBERT-base encoder and the same tokenizer configuration for consistency across features. Inputs are prepared as follows:

- **Essay-level inputs:** the essay string tokenized to 512 tokens (truncated beyond limit).
- **Sentence-pair inputs:** two consecutive sentences concatenated with special separators; pairs are derived via a sentence segmenter.
- **Regression inputs:** identical to sentence-pair inputs; the head outputs a single scalar (via the sequence-classification API), trained against continuous targets.

3.3.2 Essay-Level Classifier (Global Structure)

- **Purpose:** capture **topic/semantic** dominance, rhetorical stance, and broader discourse organization that frequently separates HUMAN from MG and, to a degree, the hybrid classes.
- **Input.** Full essay text tokenized to the model context (truncation as needed; see Appendix A for exact limits).
- **Learning objective.** Four-way classification using cross-entropy.
- Full training arguments and token limits are reported in Appendix A.

3.3.3 Sentence-Pair Classifier (Local Transitions)

- **Purpose:** detect short-range transitions—lexical/rhythmic mismatches, referential discontinuities, or stitching artifacts—that are typical when AI edits or paraphrases human or machine text and particularly informative for distinguishing HG_MOD vs MG_MOD.
- **Input:** consecutive sentence pairs aggregated across the essay.
- **Learning objective.** Four-way classification with labels inherited from the source essay.
- Pair construction, token limits, and training arguments are listed in Appendix A.

3.3.4 Coherence Scorer (Regression-Like Head)

- **Purpose:** quantify discourse flow in local context; lower predicted scores often indicate abrupt topical shifts or weak connective between sentences.
- **Input.** Adjacent sentence pairs, scored individually and averaged per essay.
- **Learning objective:** optimized as regression-like with MSE; evaluated with MSE and R^2 during validation.
- Target mapping and optimization settings are reported in Appendix A.

3.3.5 Style-Consistency Scorer (Regression-Like Head)

- **Purpose:** estimate stylistic uniformity between adjacent sentences (lexical choice, register, rhythm). Piecewise paraphrasing/polishing tends to create detectable style discontinuities, whereas unedited human or machine passages are more style-consistent.
- **Input.** Adjacent sentence pairs, scored individually and averaged per essay.
- **Learning objective:** optimized as a regression-like with MSE; evaluated with MSE and R^2 during validation.
- Target mapping and optimization settings are reported in Appendix A.

3.3.6 Training and Optimization

- **Data Splits:** 70/15/15 train/validation/test produced via stratified splitting by label; pair/derived datasets reuse the persisted splits to preserve grouping (prevents near-duplicate leakage across splits).
- **Optimizer & precision:** AdamW (fused) with fp16 mixed precision; weight decay 0.01; max_grad_norm 1.0.
- **Batching:** dynamic padding per batch; gradient accumulation 4 (essay) / 8 (pair, coherence, style)..
- **Epochs:** 5 (essay); 3 (pair, coherence, style).
- **Stability:** gradient checkpointing enabled; evaluation/saving each epoch.
- **Reproducibility/logging:** seeds fixed in scripts; checkpoints and final models saved under task-specific folders; JSON metadata emitted per run.

3.3.7 Class Handling and Length Effects

Class distributions at the essay level are reasonably balanced across the four labels; the pair/regression datasets inherit these proportions via the persisted splits. Because essays are truncated to 512 tokens, we guard against truncation artifacts by (i) preserving sentence-pair order for local tasks and (ii) validating that the distribution of essay lengths is comparable across splits (details in Appendix A). If future releases include longer contexts, the same heads can be trained with sliding windows; this is not used in the current codebase.

3.3.8 Calibration and Post-Processing

Each head outputs probabilities (classifiers) or continuous scores (regressors). While global calibration is ultimately handled during fusion (§3.3.10), we compute standard diagnostics during validation—macro/weighted F1 for classifiers and R²/MSE for regression-like heads—to monitor training and trigger early stopping. (Numerical results are reported in §4.)

3.3.9 Implementation Notes and Reproducibility

All models are implemented in PyTorch with Hugging Face Transformers. The four finetuners are modular (one script per task), share tokenization and training arguments, and write: (i) intermediate checkpoints, (ii) a `final_model` directory with weights/tokenizer, and (iii) a run metadata JSON (hyperparameters, best-epoch metric, seed). This ensures runs are repeatable and auditable across environments.

3.3.10 Multi-Class Inference via Fusion Voting

At inference, we combine the four ModernBERT heads to produce a single 4-class decision {HUMAN, MG, HG_MOD, MG_MOD}, while deliberately computing and displaying three fusion strategies side-by-side—Equal Split (50–50), Dynamic (confidence/coverage-adaptive), and Hierarchical (70–30)—without selecting a winner in code. For each essay we compute:

- **Essay-level classifier:** a 4-way probability vector.
- **Sentence-pair classifier:** per-pair 4-way probabilities averaged to one 4-way vector..
- **Coherence scorer:** per-pair scalar scores in [0,1], averaged to one value.
- **Style-consistency scorer:** per-pair scalar scores in [0,1] with binary targets {0,1} in code (1 = style-consistent, 0 = style-break), averaged to one value.

For the two scalar heads, the script maps them to per-class support using a simple complement rule:

- For HUMAN and MG, use the mean score directly.
- For HG_MOD and MG_MOD, use (1 – mean score).

Together with the two classifier vectors, are the scalar heads fused under each strategy to yield three normalized 4-way distributions that are reported side-by-side:

(A) Equal Split (50–50)

The intent is to balance global and local features equally, treating each head equally. The score is given by:

$$\text{Final} = 0.50 \cdot \text{Essay} + 0.167 \cdot \text{Pairs} + 0.167 \cdot \text{Coherence-mapped} + 0.167 \cdot \text{Style-mapped}.$$

(B) Dynamic Weighting (confidence- and coverage-adaptive)

Weights are set proportionally to simple confidence heuristics (no extra training, no explicit coverage/length multiplier):

- **Essay confidence** = essay model’s max softmax.
- **Pair confidence** = mean of the per-pair max softmax values.

- **Coherence stability** = $1 - \text{std} / \text{std}$ of per-pair coherence scores.
- **Style stability** = $1 - \text{std} / \text{std}$ of per-pair style scores.

These four numbers are normalized to produce per-branch weights (the code scales them uniformly and then renormalizes the fused 4-way vector at the end). The coherence/style scalars contribute via the complement rule ($\text{HUMAN/MG} := \text{mean score}$; $\text{HG_MOD/MG_MOD} := 1 - 1 - \text{mean}$). This strategy up-weights whichever branch is more confident or stable (sharper probabilities or low dispersion) without hard-coding any preference for longer texts.

(C) Hierarchical Fusion (70–30)

Prioritize discrete classification evidence to make the primary call, then refine with continuous signals from coherence/style at stage 2. The vector is calculated as:

- Stage 1 (70%): 50% weight to essay-level prediction + 20% each to sentence pair predictions and
- Stage 2 (30%): 15% to Coherence scores + 15% to Style consistency scores

This strategy reflects how the system is often used in practice: make a strong initial call with the two classifiers, then use coherence/style to stabilize borderline cases and hybrids.

4. Results

We present the results in two parts. First, we evaluate the Random Forest (RF) baseline trained on fixed sentence embeddings and calibrated with recall-targeted thresholds; this establishes a transparent, low-cost reference with strong pairwise diagnostics. We then evaluate the ModernBERT models reported in §4.2, showing how global, local, and continuous cues combine to improve robustness on hybrid texts. Throughout, we emphasize operating points that prioritize high recall for AI-related classes and use the validation set to fix thresholds and normalizations before testing.

4.1 Random Forest Baseline

Across the six one-vs-one (OvO) comparisons, the RF baseline provides strong discrimination on most class pairs. Pairs involving **HUMAN vs MG** and **HUMAN vs MG_MOD** are near-perfect with AUCs clustered close to 1.0, indicating that pure human writing and pure machine (or machine-rewritten machine) outputs are well separated in embedding space, illustrated in figure 4. The hybrid-vs-hybrid comparison **HG_MOD vs MG_MOD** is the most challenging, but remains learnable (median AUC ≈ 0.85), consistent with the intuition that both classes can exhibit mixed human/AI signals. See figure 5 for the ROC curves by pair and embeddings.

As expected, OpenAI (1,536-dim) slightly outperforms DistilRoBERTa (768-dim) and MiniLM (384-dim) in median AUC and high-recall stability. However, MiniLM is often within a few points of the best AUC while offering the lowest inference cost/latency—useful for CPU-only or edge deployments. DistilRoBERTa typically sits between the two, offering a good open-weights option.

Figure 4: AUC distributions by class pairs.

Figure 5: Detailed ROC curves by embedding and pair.

Selecting validation-time operating points by minimum recall targets ($\tau \in \{0.50, 0.65, 0.80\}$) provides practical control of false negatives without collapsing precision. After threshold selection, model recalls concentrate between 0.90 and 0.97, and the F1 distribution remains stable—evidence that the recall-first rule identifies useful decision cutoffs rather than merely relaxing the boundary. In multi-class inference, aggregating the six binaries with F1-Weighted voting yields balanced behavior, while the Balanced-Weighted rule shifts slightly toward protecting against missed AI by rewarding high recall more explicitly. On clearly separable cases both voting modes agree; on borderline hybrids, the recall-centric rule reduces false negatives at a

modest precision cost, which is aligned with our use case. See figures 6 and 7 for Recall and F1 distribution.

Figure 6: Recall distribution across models and threshold

Figure 7: F1 distribution across models and thresholds.

Confusions tend to arise where hybrids blur boundaries: HG_MOD vs HUMAN (when edits are light and preserve human rhythm) and MG_MOD vs MG (when a second model rewrites with similar style). The OvO formulation helps here: those ambiguous regions are handled by pair-specific decision surfaces rather than a single multiclass boundary, and their thresholds are tuned to the desired recall.

4.2 Deep Learning Models

For deep learning models, the essay-level classifier achieved high topline performance with an overall accuracy of 97.5% and weighted F1 of 0.975, with minimal confusion between Human and AI categories and errors concentrated primarily along the hybrid boundary rather than the

human-machine axis - see table 1. Class-wise recall is strongest for HUMAN and MG, while misclassifications tend to occur between HG_MOD and MG_MOD, which share editing artifacts. This establishes a strong global baseline and confirms that much of the separability is already present at the essay level.

Table 1: Essay-level classification results

Class	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
HUMAN	1.000	0.983	0.991
HG_MOD	0.985	0.997	0.991
MG	0.961	0.911	0.935
MG_MOD	0.961	0.982	0.972

The sentence-pair classifier reached solid performance when per-pair predictions were aggregated across each essay with 92.7% accuracy and F1 of 0.927, effectively capturing local coherence and stylistic continuity - see Table 2. While overall accuracy and weighted F1 are a bit lower than the essay-level model—as expected given the harder, short-range signal—the pair model provides complementary evidence on stitching and paraphrase artifacts. In particular, it helps resolve borderline cases in which an otherwise well-formed essay exhibits localized style or coherence breaks attributable to AI edits.

Table 2: Sentence-pair classification results

Class	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
HUMAN	0.979	0.981	0.980
HG_MOD	0.951	0.953	0.952
MG	0.852	0.843	0.848
MG_MOD	0.912	0.915	0.914

The confusion matrices show heavy mass on the diagonal for both essay-level and fused predictions, with the majority of residual error localized to HG_MOD ↔ MG_MOD, as anticipated - see Figure 8 for the essay level classifier results and figure 9 for the sentence-pair classifier results.

Figure 8: Confusion matrix for the essay-level classifier.

Figure 9: Confusion matrix for the pair-sentence classifier.

The coherence scorer explains a large share of variance with a $R^2 = 0.925$ with low mean-squared error of $MSE = 0.0054$, reflecting sensitivity to abrupt topical shifts and weak referential links between adjacent sentences. MG and MG_MOD are harder to separate but still show clear shifts. The overall result supports downstream use in the ensemble fusion score. See table 3 for detailed results by classes.

Table 3: Coherence scorer - regression results

Class	True Score	Mean Predicted	Std Dev	MSE
HUMAN	1.00	0.990	0.049	0.0025
HG_MOD	0.70	0.684	0.075	0.0059
MG	0.50	0.462	0.070	0.0064
MG_MOD	0.30	0.343	0.067	0.0064

Figure 10 plots the distribution of the model’s coherence scores by true class after aggregating per-pair predictions within each essay (we average the sentence-pair scores to one value in $[0,1]$ per essay). The four curves exhibit a clear ordinal pattern aligned with the training target mapping (HUMAN→1.0, HG_MOD→0.7, MG→0.5, MG_MOD→0.3): the HUMAN distribution concentrates near the upper end (high coherence), HG_MOD centers lower but remains distinct from pure machine writing, MG shifts further left, and MG_MOD anchors the lowest region. Although neighboring classes show some overlap—as expected in reflective prose—the separation is pronounced: HUMAN seldom encroaches on the MG/MG_MOD bands, and the two hybrid regimes (HG_MOD vs MG_MOD) display visibly different centers, indicating that AI edits to human text preserve more local flow than second-model rewrites of AI text.

One additional pattern is worth noting. The modal ordering of the curves mirrors the validation means used to define class compatibility in the fusion stage, but the spreads are learned—not fixed—reflecting genuine variability in local discourse continuity. Together, these distributions explain why the coherence head improves hybrid discrimination in the fused decision: its high end reinforces HUMAN calls, its low end supports MG/MG_MOD, and its mid-range helps tip borderline cases toward HG_MOD when local flow remains intact.

Figure 10: Confusion matrix for the pair-sentence classifier.

The style-consistency scorer produces a clear separation on its binary target, with strong $R^2 = 0.782$ and 93% binary accuracy at the nominal threshold of 0.5. Human + AI and AI+AI essays receive much lower scores, as expected. Particularly effective at catching stylistic breaks introduced by editing or rephrasing. See table 4 for detailed results by classes. .

Table 4: Style-consistency scorer - regression results

Class	Mean Predicted	Std Dev	MSE	Accuracy
HUMAN	0.971	0.123	0.0159	97.9%
HG_MOD	0.051	0.155	0.0267	96.8%
MG	0.764	0.289	0.1392	79.2%
MG_MOD	0.108	0.199	0.0513	94.2%

Figure 10 shows the distribution of style-consistency scores by true class after aggregating per-pair predictions to a single [0,1] value per essay (we average the adjacent-sentence scores). Because the target for this head is binary (HUMAN = 1, MG = 1, HG_MOD = 0, MG_MOD = 0; see Appendix A), the four curves organize into two broad bands with informative separation inside each band. The HUMAN and MG classes concentrate near the upper range (high consistency), reflecting a relatively uniform voice within unedited human essays and within model-generated prose. The HG_MOD and MG_MOD classes shift lower, indicating more frequent style breaks introduced by piecewise paraphrasing or polishing.

Within-band differences are also evident. The HUMAN curve typically peaks slightly higher and is narrower than MG, reflecting a more consistent voice under this constrained, reflective prompt. Conversely, MG shows a slightly lower, broader peak, consistent with the added variability we induced via prompt engineering (tones/perspectives and instruction sampling). Among the lower band, HG_MOD tends to sit above MG_MOD, suggesting that AI edits applied to human text often preserve more of the original voice than second-model rewrites of AI text. Overlap exists in the mid-range ($\approx 0.4-0.7$), which corresponds to essays with mixed cues—e.g., mostly consistent style with a few edited seams.

Figure 10: Confusion matrix for the pair-sentence classifier.

5. Discussion

Our findings suggest that domain-specific AI detection benefits significantly from combining global, local, and stylistic features. Coherence and style regressors capture subtle disruptions characteristic of AI editing, while classification models identify broader semantic patterns. Together, they enable robust differentiation even when human and AI text elements are intertwined.

From an operational perspective, recall-oriented optimization ensures minimal risk of undetected AI content, which is vital in formative and diagnostic settings. The computational footprint remains modest: ModernBERT fine-tuning and inference can be executed on consumer-grade GPUs, and the Random Forest baseline offers a viable fallback for CPU-only environments.

These results generalize beyond DAACS to other reflective or domain-specific writing contexts, such as medical case narratives, professional training logs, or ethics statements. In all cases, the framework’s modularity allows domain re-training or re-weighting without redesigning the entire pipeline.

Optimizing for high recall is preferable to risking missed AI content in diagnostic contexts. Institutions can pair the system with a lightweight review workflow: low-confidence or disagreeing cases (e.g., classifier vs. regression signals diverge) are queued for human review, while high-confidence decisions can be auto-cleared. This aligns operating points with risk tolerance and keeps uncertainty transparent.

Our evaluation is intentionally in-domain. Results reflect a single reflective prompt family (DAACS) and a specific mix of LLMs, tones, and rewriting techniques. Although we diversified generation settings, real usage evolves quickly. Deployments to new prompts or venues should include a small calibration set and threshold tuning to re-anchor operating points.

The hybrid labels approximate human–AI collaboration through controlled rewriting. This can bias detectors toward artifacts of our synthesis recipes. We mitigated risk by varying LLM families/versions, instructions, tones, and perspectives, but future work should incorporate naturally occurring human–AI edits when ethically feasible.

Periodic re-benchmarking (e.g., quarterly) should refresh MG/MG_MOD sets with current models, recompute validation normalizations for inference-time fusion, and re-select RF thresholds. Versioned datasets and persisted metadata make these updates routine.

Adversarial evasion remains possible (e.g., aggressive paraphrase with coherence smoothing). The multi-view design reduces single-signal failures by combining global, local, and continuous cues, but a defensive approach is still prudent: randomize prompts for confirmation checks, monitor unusual length/coverage patterns, and, where acceptable, complement with provenance signals.

A practical advantage of the approach is auditability. Each decision can surface per-branch evidence (essay/posterior, pair aggregate, coherence/style scalars) alongside the three fusion outputs. Presenting this panel to reviewers supports reasoned overrides and makes periodic calibration straightforward.

6. Conclusion

This paper introduced a domain-specific framework for detecting AI-generated and hybrid essays, using DAACS as a case study. The approach combines a recall-tuned Random Forest baseline with four ModernBERT heads that capture global document signals, local sentence transitions, and continuous coherence/style cues. Simple inference-time fusion (Equal, Dynamic, Hierarchical) produces transparent multi-class decisions without additional training.

Empirically, the RF OvO baseline provides strong pairwise separability and controllable operating points; the deep models further improve robustness on hybrid regimes. Essay-level classification achieves high accuracy/F1, sentence-pair modeling contributes complementary local evidence, and the coherence/style heads supply interpretable continuous signals that stabilize borderline cases. The resulting system is computationally modest and suitable for deployment in formative settings that prioritize high recall and auditability.

While our datasets and prompts are in-domain, the methodology generalizes to other reflective or specialized writing contexts. Future work should extend coverage to new prompts and emerging LLMs, incorporate naturally occurring human–AI edits, and harden the pipeline against deliberate evasion—while maintaining the same lightweight, inference-time fusion design.

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